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GONet all sky camera calibration

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Abstract

This report presents the results of characterization tests made to the GoNET all-sky light pollution camera. The results show remarkable sensor linearity, noticeable vignetting, good optical axis alignment, traces of on-chip signal processing, spectral response according to the sensor curve provided by the manufacturer in the B and G channels except for a severe cut-off from 590 nm on in the R channel, a photon transfer behavior consistent with a typical CMOS device and also highlights the importance of good flat fielding for precise photometry measurements. Along the process, we have developed a series of analysis tools that could be applied to other imaging devices such as DSLR cameras.

1. Introduction and Setup

In November, 2023 the LICA staff received a request to characterize the GONet camera, an all-sky, low cost light pollution monitoring system [1] based on a Raspberry Pi Zero W hardware with an attached Raspberry Pi HQ Camera and a wide angle lens (figure 1).

Figure 1: The GONet light pollution monitoring system

The GONet camera is a turnkey system designed to perform autonomous capture, analysis and publication of light pollution measurements. The GONet team (Adler Planetarium) provided us with a way to connect to the device via SSH, disable the automatic capture and proceed with our own capture scripts. These were based on the well known `rastipill` command line utility which allows capturing still images in RAW format with total control of acquisition parameters. This utility allows defining both an analog gain and a digital gain for the capture. Throughout all our data acquisition, we have set the digital gain to 1 (it is just a multiplier in the digital domain) and an analog gain to 1 to maximize dynamic range. This analog gain appears in the various plots as ISO 6, as reported by the underlying LibRaw library [13].

The optical workbench at LICA (Laboratorio de Instrumentación Científica Avanzada, Universidad Complutense de Madrid) is a versatile tool that allows to characterize filter transmissions, quantum efficiencies and spectral response of imaging detectors. It consists of a high power quartz lamp (100W) emitting in a wide range of wavelengths, controlled by a constant voltage power supply. The light is channeled first to a series of filter wheels, the first one mounted with different Neutral Density (ND) filters acting as attenuators. The second wheel mounts different bandpass filters designed to avoid second-order spectra sneaking into the output of a monochromator. After the filter wheels, a grating scanning spectrometer monochromator allows us to select the desired wavelength with 1 nm resolution. The monochrome output of the spectrometer can be used in several ways. Figure 2 shows the setup mounted for characterizing the GONet camera. The monochromatic light is fed into an integrating sphere whose purpose is to diffuse light and simultaneously mount two devices in different ports. In this case the reference device (a calibrated photodiode) and the GoNET camera.

Figure 2: The GONet camera (far left) attached to the left port of the integrating sphere. On the top, a reference photodiode connected by coaxial cable to a pico-ammeter. The white box is the monochromator which is illuminated by the lamp (far right) through the filter wheels (in black),

Then output ports (holes) in the integrating sphere are covered with a diffuse glass resulting in uniform surfaces on which to perform exposures. The resulting light is monochromatic and with the same intensity in both ports. The wavelength can be selected with the scanning

spectrometer. We chose to use 500 nm green light to perform linearity tests on the green channels with satisfactory results.

In principle, the aim of the characterization was mainly to obtain the camera spectral response. However, after finding similar works characterizing the same sensor [2], we decided to extend the scope of characterization to other interesting aspects such as linearity, pre-processing traces and Photon Transfer Curves (PTCs) with the goal of replicating the same results.

The following sections will present the reader with the results of the following camera aspects: linearity, pre-processing traces, PTCs and spectral response. Although the processing can be made in parallel for all R, Gr, B and Gb channels comprising the Bayer pattern, most of the time will focus on the Gr channel. The different plots were generated with Matplotlib [8].

2. Vignetting and Optical alignment

Vignetting is a radial gradient brightness (in an otherwise flat image) from the optical center caused by the optical train in front of the detector. This effect increases as the optical focal decreases, which is the case of the wide field GONet camera.

Figure 3. GONet exposure at mid range in the green channels. The panels show the images corresponding to the R,Gr, Gb, and B channels of the Bayer matrix. ROI statistics are given without black level subtraction. Central 'x' shows the sensor center. Large cross regions are used for optical centroid calculation.

Figure 3 shows a typical flat field where noticeable vignetting can be seen in all four R, Gr, Gb and B channels, due to the wide angle lens mounted on the camera.

Figure 4 shows a contour plot of the Gr channel in figure 3 exhibiting radial symmetry, a sign of lack of optical problems. Radial cut profiles along the H & V axis were performed using the "extended" ROIs shown in figure 3. The optical center can be calculated as the centroid of these profiles and be compared to the sensor (geometrical) center. Figure 5 shows such radial profiles as well as the optical and geometrical center. The results showed a slight misalignment of about 7 pixels in the H axis (0.3% of 2028 pixels in total) and negligible misalignment on the V axis. Taking into account that the fisheye lens has a focal length (FL)

of 1.55 mm, the plate scale P for the image is $P = 206265 / FL = 133074 \text{ arcsec} / \text{mm}$. Since the IMX477 has an original pixel size of 1.55 μm (3.10 μm in each color plane after debayering), the plate scale is 413 arcsec/pixel. The H misalignment expressed in physical units is 1.24 arcsec.

flatX_g01_046_2600300_a.jpg
RaspberryPi RP_imx477, ISO: 6
Color Plane Size: 2028 cols x 1520 rows

Figure 4. Gr channel contour plot. Image was previously filtered with a 2D 11x11 low-pass filter to better display contour lines.

flatX_g01_046_2600300_a.jpg
RaspberryPi RP_imx477, ISO: 6
Color Plane Size: 2028 cols x 1520 rows

flatX_g01_046_2600300_a.jpg
RaspberryPi RP_imx477, ISO: 6
Color Plane Size: 2028 cols x 1520 rows

Figure 5.(Upper) Marginal distributions along H & V regions plotted in figure 3. (Lower). Zoomed view showing optical (centroid) and geometric (sensor) centers. The H (blue) curve shows different optical vs geometrical alignment centers.

3. Linearity

The sensor mounted in the GONet camera is a Sony IMX477 device. It is a back-illuminated CMOS sensor with up to 12 bit A/D converter in some of its operating modes. The underlying software (`LibRaw` [13]) reports a black level of 256 on all Bayer channels that is removed during processing. The goal of this section is to verify its linearity. An exposure with the camera results in a digital file with the color image. After the Bayer matrix color separation (“debayering”), each one of the 4 color channels can be analyzed. Because of vignetting, the statistics for image linearity are taken in a central Region of Interest (ROI), small enough to mitigate such vignetting but large enough for statistical purposes (10000 pixels approx.)

Once this ROI was defined, we proceeded to take a series of exposures of varying time. Since we wanted to focus on both ends of the exposure range, we developed an exposure plan that took far more images and both sides of the scale (figure 6). Up to 91 exposures were taken: exposure length from a minimum time of 600 μ s to 5.2 seconds. The upper limit was set by iterating up to a point where we could show the beginning of saturation.

Figure 6. Linearity exposure plan showing image sequence number versus exposure time.

The results of the exposure time versus signal level for all channels are shown in figure 7. As expected, given that the exposure was made with 500 nm monochromatic light, the Gr and

Gb channels saturate at 4.9 sec. approximately while the B channel is in the mid-range range and the R channel barely shows any signal.

Figure 7. Signal level [DN] versus exposure time [s]. Black levels have been subtracted from raw signal levels in the processing. The saturation point was defined as the threshold in which $SNR \approx 100$.

The measured linearity curve shows a hard knee, indicating that the saturation comes from the maximum value offered by the 12 bit A/D converter. This acknowledges the specs given in [2] as 4095 as the raw saturation point for the Pi HQ Camera (3839 after black level subtraction).

3.1. Saturation

In figure 7, we can observe some points (orange) being flagged as saturated before linear fitting. The saturation point is a threshold calculated by visual estimation of a Signal To Noise Ratio (SNR) vs mean Signal level curve (one of the curves used in the Photon Transfer Curves technique described below). Figure 8 shows this curve and the hard knee where the saturation regime starts for this particular ROI.

SNR (Total Noise) vs. Signal
 RaspberryPi RP_imx477, ISO: 6
 Color Plane Size: 2028 cols x 1520 rows
 ROI: [712:807,963:1064] 101 cols x 95 rows

Figure 8. Signal to Noise Ratio versus mean Signal level. Saturation level starts at $SNR \approx 100$.

4. HV Spectrograms

Spectrograms show a visual depiction of the power (energy in case of images) distribution across frequencies (spatial frequencies in case of images). They are quite sensitive to non-random changes of signal along dimensions, (horizontal and vertical in case of images). Since pixels are precisely aligned with the horizontal and vertical dimensions (H&V), image spectrograms are an ideal tool to detect some kind of preprocessing before the image is written to the file. It is not infrequent that advanced CMOS sensors may include some kind of pre-processing to the raw image in an effort to reduce noise at low light levels. In fact, this is one of the claims made by [2] regarding the Sony IMX477 sensor.

The energy spectrogram ES for an image is defined as the squared module of its 2D discrete Fourier transform :

$$ES(h, v) = |FFT(Image(x, y))|^2 \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

We used Python Numpy [7] for the images analysis. Numpy's FFT (fast fourier transform) implementation for an 2D NxM array yields another NxM 2D complex array. As stated in Numpy's documentation, the first N/2xM/2 are the positive frequency terms up to the Nyquist frequency, discarding the rest are symmetrical, negative frequencies. Once $ES(h, v)$ is computed, we aggregated the 2D array into two unidimensional vectors along the H & V axes to highlight processing in these two specific directions.

$$H(h) = \frac{2}{M} \sum_{v=0}^{v=M/2} ES(h, v) ; h = 0..N/2 \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

$$V(v) = \frac{2}{N} \sum_{h=0}^{h=N/2} ES(h, v) ; v = 0..M/2$$

Finally, to better represent these two H & V vectors in the same figure, we normalized its coordinates from integers to a [0..0.5] range¹ so that we can plot both vectors independent from their real dimensions and 0.5 is the normalized Nyquist frequency for each axis.

We generated a synthetic dark frame generated with a random number generator using a gaussian distribution whose $\sigma = 1.536$. Figure 9 depicts its HV spectrogram as a flat, noisy distribution with no special features.

Image: dark_g01_001_0000600_a.jpg
 RaspberryPi RP_imx477, ISO: 6
 Color Plane Size: 2028 cols x 1520 rows
 ROI: [0:1520,0:2028] 2028 cols x 1520 rows

Figure 9. Gr channel. HV spectrogram for a synthetic gaussian, random noise dark frame.

When taking a real dark frame - although the image itself seemed identical - its HV diagram is quite different. Figure 10 shows S shaped curves with more energy response in the lower spatial frequencies, suggesting some kind of low pass filtering is made, as claimed by [2]. Our original HV spectrograms showed a strong peak at 0 in both directions and this compressed all the plots. Removing the first two components in both vectors made our plots

¹ The Nyquist frequency is 0.5 of the pixel pitch frequency.

almost identical as [2] spectrograms. Also, our V curve (orange) also shows an additional fringing effect (electrical interference?) not present in [2].

Figure 10. Gr channel. HV Spectrogram for a real dark frame. Its S-shaped form hints at some kind of preprocessing.

5. Photon Transfer Curves

5.1. The simplified detector model

The Photon Transfer Curves (PTC) [4] are a well-known methodology used to design, characterize, calibrate or optimize solid state imagers (mainly CCD and CMOS sensors) or camera systems based on them. Only a subset of these curves are used in this report and our aim was to characterize the main parameters of a simplified detector model. This model is characterized by the following noise sources:

- **Readout Noise** (σ_{READ}). All noise sources not related to the signal, mainly the different electronics subsystems involved in the image readout. This noise is a constant factor that must be empirically determined.
- **Signal Shot Noise** (σ_{SHOT}). Noise produced by the interacting photons. This noise is described by the classical Poisson probability distribution $\sigma_{SHOT} = \sqrt{\eta_i S}$ where η_i is the quantum yield and S is the mean signal level in electrons. According to [4], the

quantum yield $\eta_i(\lambda)$ is 1 for photon energies from 1.14 eV to 3.1 eV (wavelengths from 1100 nm to 400 nm respectively). For energies greater than 3.1 eV, the interacting photon will usually generate more than one electron on average but there is no simple energy-to-quantum-yield equation for photon energies in the range from 3.1 eV to 10 eV.

- **Fixed Pattern Noise (σ_{FPN}).** Not all pixels behave equally across the sensor, yielding to pixel-to-pixel variations. The tag “fixed” comes from the fact that it is a spatially dependent but not random variation and can be eliminated with suitable processing techniques. The simplified detector model empirically models this noise source as a percentage p_N of the mean signal level: $\sigma_{FPN} = p_N S$. According to [4], a typical value for this quality factor in modern CCD/CMOS imagers is 0.01 (1% rms noise respect to the mean signal level).

These noise sources (expressed in electrons) add in quadrature (variances) as they are uncorrelated:

$$\sigma_{TOT}^2 = \sigma_{READ}^2 + \sigma_{SHOT}^2 + \sigma_{FPN}^2 \quad [e^-] \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

Substituting the various terms presented before into eq. 3:

$$\sigma_{TOT}^2 = \sigma_{READ}^2 + \eta_i S + p_N^2 S^2 \quad [e^-] \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

Since our artifacts are digitized images, it is convenient to express this relation in digital numbers (DN), taking into account that we can relate the signal or noise levels in electrons with its DN counterparts through a convenient gain factor g in e^-/DN as follows: $X_{e^-} = g X_{DN}$. This conversion factor must also be determined empirically along the process. Our tests are being made with 500 nm monochromatic light, so we can safely assume that $\eta_i = 1$ and our detector noise model can be expressed in DN units as follows:

$$\sigma_{TOT}^2 = \sigma_{READ}^2(DN) + S_{DN}/g + p_N^2 S_{DN}^2 \quad [DN] \quad (\text{Eq. 5})$$

where S_{DN} is the signal level in DN and the adjustable parameters in our model are:

- $\sigma_{READ}^2(DN)$, the measured readout noise, expressed in DN
- g , the system gain in e^-/DN
- p_N , the FPN quality factor (%).

Taking the last detector noise model (Eq. 5) as a basis, we can identify four different noise regimes:

- A low light region where the dominant source is the readout noise $\sigma_{READ}^2(DN)$.
- a moderate light region where the shot noise $\sigma_{SHOT} = \sqrt{\frac{S_{DN}}{g}}$ is the predominant source noise, because the FPN is still negligible.

- a highly illuminated region where the FPN noise $\sigma_{FPN} = p_N S_{DN}$ is the predominant noise source if p_N is high enough.
- a saturated image region where the total noise σ_{TOT} falls abruptly due to pixel saturation.

Unlike the work presented in [2] where the simplified detector model parameters are estimated all at once by multivariate regression analysis on a SNR vs Signal PTC curve similar to figure 8, our estimation is done in steps, using two different PTC curves.

5.2. Image pairs technique

To analyze the different regimes, we need to separate the different noise sources. The fixed pattern noise (FPN) can be easily canceled by taking image pairs of the same exposure time and subtracting them. By error propagation rules, this subtracted image pair doubles its variance with respect to the single images. This variance σ_{PAIR} consists only of readout and shot noise, so that:

$$\sigma_{READ+SHOT}^2 = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{PAIR}^2 \quad [DN] \quad (\text{Eq. 6})$$

where σ_{PAIR} is the measured variance of the subtracted image pair. A separate measurement of total noise σ_{TOT}^2 in a single image of a pair yields an excess noise due to FPN, thus being estimated as:

$$\sigma_{FPN}^2 = \sigma_{TOT}^2 - \sigma_{READ+SHOT}^2 \quad [DN] \quad (\text{Eq. 7})$$

If we further estimate σ_{READ} by other means, then:

$$\sigma_{SHOT}^2 = \sigma_{READ+SHOT}^2 - \sigma_{READ}^2 \quad [DN] \quad (\text{Eq. 8})$$

Since we have characterized all three noise sources, we can plot and identify the different regimes explained above.

5.3. Gain estimation

By eliminating the fixed pattern noise by the image pairs technique, we can derive a simpler total noise variance equation with only readout noise and shot noise variances:

$$\sigma_{READ+SHOT}^2 = \sigma_{READ}^2(DN) + S_{DN}/g \quad [DN] \quad (\text{Eq. 9})$$

in which $\sigma_{READ+SHOT}^2$ is a linear function of S_{DN} with slope $m = 1/g$ and intercept value $b = \sigma_{READ}^2(DN)$

$\sigma_{READ+SHOT}^2$ vs. Signal
 RaspberryPi RP_imx477, ISO: 6
 Color Plane Size: 2028 cols x 1520 rows
 ROI: [712:807,963:1064] 101 cols x 95 rows

Figure 11. Gr channel. $\sigma_{READ+SHOT}^2$ versus mean signal level S_{DN} showing a linear fit from signal level 50 to 3300.

Figure 11 is a Photon Transfer Curve (PTC) showing noise variance vs signal level as well as the orange selection points for the fitted line from which we estimated the system gain as $g = 2.32 e^-/DN$. Comparing the value of $\sigma_{READ}^2(DN)$ with an estimation of readout noise from a bias image with the same ROI, we have discarded the intercept estimation of $\sigma_{READ}^2(DN)$ as not reliable.

5.4. Readout noise estimation

The readout noise can be estimated either by taking a bias image and measuring its mean signal level in the ROI or by plotting the total noise σ_{TOT} against the mean signal level S_{DN} using the same ROI as the one used in the linearity plot.

Individual Noise Sources vs. Signal
 RaspberryPi RP_imx477, ISO: 6
 Color Plane Size: 2028 cols x 1520 rows
 ROI: [712:807,963:1064] 101 cols x 95 rows

Figure 12. Gr channel. Total noise σ_{TOT} (blue), combined $\sigma_{READ+SHOT}$ noise (orange) and σ_{FPN} (green) vs mean signal level S_{DN} . Note the abrupt decay due to saturation.

Figure 12 is a Noise vs Signal PTC. In this figure, we estimated the read noise $\sigma_{READ}(DN)$ by visual inspection using the matplotlib cursor taking the leftmost orange datapoint (whose $y = 1.536$). It is worth mentioning that for the same ROI as used in the linearity plots, the shot noise component dominates the moderate to high level signal up to the saturation point. The saturation region is short and abrupt due to the digital nature of the IMX477 saturation (A/D overflow).

5.5. FPN quality factor estimation

Any FPN point (shown in green) in the high signal regime of figure 12 could be used to estimate this parameter by visual inspection using the matplotlib cursor and applying the formula:

$$p_N = \sigma_{FPN} / S_{DN} \quad (\text{Eq. 10})$$

However, we preferred to select a sample of these points and calculated the average p_N . Figure 13 shows the result of such selection in the range of S_{DN} from 500 up to 3300. The resulting $p_N = 0.00979$ matches very well the typical values stated in [4].

Figure 13. Green Gr channel. σ_{FPN} versus mean signal S_{DN} . Selected data points for p_N estimates are highlighted in yellow.

Note also that the plotted relation $\sigma_{FPN} = p_N S_{DN}$ transforms into a linear equation in a log-log plot (figure 13) whose slope is $m = 1$ and intercept value is $b = \log(p_N)$. As with the case of the readout noise estimation, we discarded estimating p_N from the intercept value because it was too sensitive to slope variations.

5.6. Vignetting and FPN

In the context of the simplified detector model, vignetting can be treated as a very low spatial frequency FPN. We increased the central ROI from 1/16 of full frame height and 1/20 of full frame width to 1/4 of full frame height and 1/5 of full frame width (figure 14) to make sure we included vignetting effects.

flatX_g01_046_2600300_a.jpg
 RaspberryPi RP_imx477, ISO: 6
 Color Plane Size: 2028 cols x 1520 rows
 ROI: [570:950,811:1217] 406 cols x 380 rows

Figure 14. Same image as figure 3 but with a significantly larger ROI $\frac{1}{3}$ and $\frac{1}{4}$ of image full width and height respectively.

The gain and readout noise parameters remain the same. However, we recalculated $p_N = \frac{\sigma_{FPN}}{S_{DN}}$ as in the section above. The new $p_N = 0.0638$ is 6.5 times larger than the original and shows how vignetting is indeed a FPN noise component.

σ_{FPN} vs. Signal
 RaspberryPi RP_imx477, ISO: 6
 Color Plane Size: 2028 cols x 1520 rows
 ROI: [570:950,811:1217] 406 cols x 380 rows

Figure 15. Green Gr channel. Large ROI σ_{FPN} noise versus S_{DN} . Orange data points have been used for p_N estimation.

With this new ROI and parameter estimation, a new PTC is shown in figure 16. The two black vertical lines divide the theoretical read noise, shot noise and FPN regimes and match well what we observe in practice. From $S_{DN} \approx 8$ the shot noise σ_{SHOT} begins dominating the readout noise σ_{READ} and σ_{FPN} is the main noise source component from $S_{DN} \approx 100$ highlighting the influence of vignetting in the ROI. Also, as predicted in the simplified detector model, the log-log plot show a quite good fit between the data points and the theoretical σ_{FPN} and σ_{SHOT} slopes up to the saturation point.

Individual Noise Sources vs. Signal
 RaspberryPi RP_imx477, ISO: 6
 Color Plane Size: 2028 cols x 1520 rows
 ROI: [570:950,811:1217] 406 cols x 380 rows

Figure 16. Green Gr channel. Results using the large ROI. Total noise σ_{TOT} (blue), read noise σ_{READ} (blue horizontal line), shot noise σ_{SHOT} (orange) and FPN σ_{FPN} (green) vs mean signal level S_{DN} .

6. Spectral Response

We have determined the GONet camera spectral response by measuring the signal of images taken with different monochromatic light using the scanning feature of the monochromator spectrometer in the range 350 nm to 1050 nm.

The reference photodiode we used is an OSI-11-01-004-10D whose responsivity and quantum efficiency QE are depicted in figure 18, left. This model's responsivity was derived from our calibrated master reference photodiode (a Hamamatsu S2281-04, calibrated at NPL) performing a cross-calibration run.

With a first exposure, the maximum exposure time before saturation was estimated. We used the same small ROI as in the linearity case in the center of the image where the maximum signal is reached. To maximize SNR in the green channels we settled on a final exposure time of 4.8 seconds, 50% greater than in the first pass and still allowing some headroom to avoid saturation. Results are shown in figure 17,

Draft Spectral Response plot
 RaspberryPi RP_imx477, ISO: 6
 Color Plane Size: 2028 cols x 1520 rows
 ROI: [712:807,963:1064] 101 cols x 95 rows

Figure 17. Raw signal at different wavelengths measured in images obtained with 4.8s exposure time. Note discontinuity in 570 nm due to bandpass filters change.

In figure 17, we can observe that both Gr and Gb channels have the same spectral response peaking at 530 nm approx. The discontinuity in the spectral response is due to the change of bandpass filters. The spectral response is virtually zero from 680 nm, suggesting that the GONet camera mounts an IR-cut filter.

Figure 18. (Left) OSI photodiode Responsivity and QE versus wavelength. (Right) Reference photodiode signal (4.8 s exposure time) at different wavelengths. Note discontinuities due to filters change at 570 nm and 860 nm

The corrected spectral response is obtained by dividing the spectral response by the photodiode response (figure 18, right), this one also corrected by its quantum efficiency (figure 18, left).

Figure 19. GONet camera calibrated spectral response, normalized respect to peak.

Figure 20. Sony IMX477 spectral response (from manufactured datasheet [3])

Comparing figures 19 & 20, we can see a remarkable coincidence in the relative response of B and Gr/Gb channels. Not only the peaks are similar but also the secondary R peak at 530 nm and the rising R and G slopes at 400 nm. However, the camera R response is severely attenuated compared to the IMX477 response. According to the Raspberry Pi HQ documentation [5], this model mounts a Hoya CM-500 infrared filter [6] and the fisheye lens mounts another 650 nm IR filter.

7. Tools

During the course of this analysis, we have developed our own tools for capturing and analyzing the images taken with the setup described in the Introduction and Setup sections.

The image capture tools are shell scripts based on the `raspistill` command line, intended to be deprecated and the reason is that it uses proprietary code from the GPU. There are other ways to capture images in the RaspberryPi ecosystem such as the newer `libcamera` C API and `picamera2` Python bindings. However, for resource constrained devices such as the Raspberry Pi Zero-W like the one mounted on the GONet camera, this is the most efficient solution since most of the capturing process is handled by the GPU and not the CPU itself.

The analysis tools have been crafted into a Python package, available at our GitHub repository [14]. They are based on other well-known packages such as `rawpy` [12] (reading RAW images and associated metadata) , `exifread` [11] (reading additional EXIF

metadata), `numpy` [7] (general purpose image math), `astropy` [9] (FITS I/O, low-pass filtering), `scikit-learn` [10] (robust fitting routines) and `matplotlib` [8] (diagram plots). In particular, `rawpy` allows us to perform analysis on other images coming from DSLR cameras as long as their RAW format can be handled by `LibRaw` (the underlying C library `rawpy` depends on).

It is far beyond this report's scope to describe these tools in detail. However, we include here the command line used to recreate the figures included in this report. The dataset on which this report is based can be found in [15]

The raw image display in figure 3 was generated with the following command:

```
rawplot-image --console pixels -i dataset/linear/flatX_g01_046_2600300_a.jpg -he 1/16 -wi 1/20 --extended-roi
```

The Gr channel Gr contour plot on figure 4, generated by:

```
rawplot-image --console contour -i dataset/linear/flatX_g01_046_2600300_a.jpg -he 1/4 -wi 1/5 --filter 11 -c Gr --labels
```

H & V cuts to show vignetting on figure 5, generated by:

```
rawplot-image --console optical -i dataset/linear/flatX_g01_046_2600300_a.jpg -he 1/16 -wi 1/20 -c Gr
```

The capture plan for the linearity study in figure 6, generated by:

```
rawplot-plan --console combistops -ti 600/1000000 -tf 5200000/1000000 -m 4095 -ppl 5
```

The linearity graphs in figure 7 were made with the following command:

```
rawplot-linearity --console -i dataset/linear/ -f flatX* -wi 1/20 -he 1/16 --snr 100
```

The saturation SNR on figure 8 was obtained by the following command:

```
rawplot-ptc --console curve6 -i dataset/linear/ -f flat* -wi 1/20 -he 1/16 -c Gr
```

The synthetic image HV spectrogram in figure 9 was generated with the following command:

```
rawplot-hv --console energy -i dataset/linear/dark/dark_g01_001_0000600_a.jpg -c
Gr --sim-read-noise 1.538
```

The real bias image HV spectrogram in figure 10 was generated using the following command:

```
rawplot-hv --console energy -i dataset/linear/dark/dark_g01_001_0000600_a.jpg -c
Gr --start 2
```

Variance PTC for gain estimation, using small ROI shown in figure 11 was generated by:

```
rawplot-ptc --console curve5 -i dataset/linear/ -f flat* -wi 1/20 -he 1/16 --fit
--from 50 --to 3300 -c Gr
```

The PTC showing the three different noise sources with small ROI in figure 12, generated by:

```
rawplot-ptc --console curve1 -i dataset/linear/ -f flat* -c Gr -wi 1/20 -he 1/16
```

Estimating the p-FPN parameter with a small (figure 13) and large (figure 15) ROI, generated by:

```
rawplot-ptc --console curve4 -i dataset/linear/ -f flat* -c Gr -wi 1/20 -he 1/16
-rd 1.536 --p-fpn estimate -fr 500 -to 3300

rawplot-ptc --console curve4 -i dataset/linear/ -f flat* -c Gr -wi 1/5 -he 1/4
-rd 1.536 --p-fpn estimate -fr 50 -to 3000
```

The big ROI image in figure 14 can be seen as:

```
rawplot-image --console pixels -i dataset/linear/flatX_g01_055_4631316_a.jpg -wi
1/5 -he 1/4
```

The full PTC with all estimated parameters in figure 16 is obtained as follows:

```
rawplot-ptc --console curve1 -i dataset/linear/ -f flat* -c Gr -wi 1/5 -he 1/4
-rd 1.536 -gn 2.32 --p-fpn 0.0638
```

Photodiode responsivity and raw readings in figure 18 were generated by:

```
rawplot-photodiode --console plot -m OSI-11-01-004-10D -r 5  
  
rawplot-spectral --console photodiode -w -m OSI-11-01-004-10D -r 5 -cv  
dataset/spectral/Gonet_photodiode_readings.csv
```

Raw and corrected GONet camera spectral response in figures 17 and 19 were generated by:

```
rawplot-spectral --console raw -wi 1/20 -he 1/16 -i dataset/spectral/ -f spec*  
  
rawplot-spectral --console corrected -wi 1/20 -he 1/16 -i dataset/spectral/ -f  
spec* -cv dataset/spectral/Gonet_photodiode_readings.csv
```

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9. References

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